

DEFORMATION MECHANISMS OF ENGINEERED FABRICS DURING PREFORM MANUFACTURE

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ABSTRACT

Liquid moulding processes including resin transfer moulding (RTM) and structural reaction injection moulding (SRIM) are now finding widespread application in the automotive industry. These processes involve the injection of liquid resin into a fibre preform, which is usually produced by forming fibre mats or fabrics between matched moulds. Structurally demanding applications usually rely on "zero-crimp" engineered fabrics consisting of two or more groups of fibres stitched together using embroidery techniques. The preform manufacturing process involves fibre movement and re-orientation which can have a significant effect on processing and structural properties. This paper describes the development of a deformation model to predict the distribution of fibres within the preform. This is based on the assumption that the fabric deforms by inter-fibre shear at the fibre crossovers or stitch centres. Reinforcement deformation is characterised for both generic and complex geometries using an automatic strain measurement system (originally developed to characterise sheet metal deformations). This allows the fibre orientations within three-dimensional preforms to be determined, and allows the validity of the process model to be established for a range of materials and geometries.

INTRODUCTION

Liquid moulding processes are becoming increasingly popular for the manufacture of structural and semi-structural components from composite materials. One of the major benefits is perceived to be the separation of reinforcement preparation from the moulding cycle by the use of reinforcement preforms. The most common method of preform manufacture involves the forming of reinforcements between matched moulds. Reinforcements may consist of either random or aligned fibres, with the latter preferred for structurally demanding components. In particular, the use of engineered fabrics, consisting of aligned fibres stitched together to provide a zero-crimp reinforcement, is increasingly popular for structural applications due to improved in-plane mechanical properties over woven materials.

Although forming operations based on engineered fabrics are more appropriate than alternative preform manufacturing routes, there are a number of associated problems. The formability of these materials is limited by the fibre architecture, with problems such as preform wrinkling observed in deep-draw components [1]. Fibre re-orientation during preform manufacture can also result in a significant departure from anticipated processing and performance properties [2]. For these reasons, in recent years a number of authors have presented simulations of aligned fibre reinforcement deformation, usually based on a kinematic mapping of fibres to a 3D surface [2-7]. However there appears to have been relatively little effort to characterise fabric deformation experimentally. The purpose of this study is to compare the deformation observed in engineered fabrics with that predicted using the kinematic modelling approach. This is achieved using an automated strain analysis system originally developed to characterise sheet metal formability. By applying this to engineered fabrics formed to various component geometries, it is possible to assess the accuracy of the model and to establish formability limits.

REINFORCEMENT DEFORMATION MODELLING

Deformation modelling for aligned reinforcements is usually based on the assumption that deformation is restricted to inter-fibre shear [3-6]. In reality, a number of mechanisms are available including shear, relative slip, fibre extension and fibre buckling (leading to wrinkling). Fig. 1 demonstrates the first two mechanisms, which are thought to be dominant for most practical forming operations. Fibre extension may be considered negligible for reinforcements based on high modulus fibres. As described in the previous section, preform wrinkling has been observed for a number of components. In the absence of fibre slip, wrinkling will occur when the fabric is sheared beyond its physical limit. This may be anticipated by measuring a fibre locking angle, which is likely to be a fabric specific property.

Figure 1. Fabric deformation mechanisms

Assuming that inter-fibre shear is the only available mechanism, the fabric can be approximated as a pin-jointed net. Based on this assumption, a deformation modelling package has been developed at the University of Nottingham [2,7]. The position of every fibre is determined using a kinematic draping algorithm, based on solving the equations of intersection between the fabric and the surface to be draped (ie the preforming tool). The surface is modelled using triangular and quadrilateral flat patches, allowing the equations to be solved explicitly. To obtain a unique draped pattern, two intersecting fibres are constrained to the surface. These are defined by geodesic paths intersecting at the point of initial contact between the reinforcement and the preforming tools.

The drape simulation has been applied to a number of complex components. An example is shown in Fig. 2, which illustrates the predicted fibre pattern for one quarter of an automotive wheel-hub draped with a $0/90^\circ$ reinforcement grid. Maximum deformation is predicted mid-way along the circumference of the component, with a minimum inter-fibre angle of 28° . This level of shear would be expected to result in reinforcement wrinkling during preform manufacture.

Figure 2. Automotive wheel-hub draped with 0/90° fabric

EXPERIMENTAL DEFORMATION ANALYSIS

Although several authors have developed deformation models similar to that described above, relatively little experimental evidence has been published to support this approach. To establish the validity of the model, a technique is required to measure the fibre positions and orientations within a deformed fabric. This could also be used to characterise the deformation mechanisms exhibited by a particular reinforcement.

EXISTING TECHNIQUES

Previous studies by the authors have established a number of techniques which can be used to validate the model [2]:

(a) Fibre volume fraction variation

One measurable effect of reinforcement shear is a local increase in fibre volume fraction. This can be estimated at each fibre crossover using the following equation:

$$V_f = \frac{S_0}{\rho t_0 \sin\beta} \quad (1)$$

where S_0 is the original stack superficial density, ρ is the fibre density, t_0 is the component thickness and β is the local inter-fibre angle. This relationship can be used to predict the average volume fraction for elements within the surface model. By carrying out burn-off tests on moulded components, the predicted variation can be compared with experimental measurements. This is demonstrated by Fig. 3 for the wheel-hub described earlier, produced by SRIM using five layers of Tech Textiles E-LT 1134 0/90° reinforcement. For this particular fabric and geometry, the correlation between theoretical and experimental volume fractions is extremely good. However this method only provides average properties related to the fibre distribution, and does not give information on local fibre orientations.

Figure 3. Fibre volume fraction variation around wheel-hub rim

(b) Visual comparison

By marking fibres within the reinforcement stack prior to preform manufacture, it is possible to compare the predicted and actual fibre patterns. This is demonstrated in Fig. 4 for the wheel-hub, on which fibres have been marked at 18 mm spacings. In this example, warp and weft tows were marked on the top fabric layer, and these were clearly visible after moulding. A qualitative comparison with the predicted pattern indicates the accuracy of the model for this component. This technique would show more potential if the fibre orientations could be measured with reasonable accuracy.

Figure 4. Predicted and actual fibre patterns for wheel-hub

AUTOMATED STRAIN ANALYSIS

A method has been developed based on measuring the deformation of a square grid printed onto the fabric, based on a technique developed by the Formability Research Group at Ford Motor Company. Such techniques have been used for a number of years to assess sheet metal formability, and in particular to establish the forming limit diagram for a particular material [8]. In the past, the deformation of such a grid would be measured manually using a

travelling microscope. However an automated system has been developed, known as the CAMSYS Automated Strain Analysis and Measurement Environment (ASAME). This involves the capture of digital images of the deformed grid from two views. These images are combined using PC based software to give the three-dimensional coordinates of each grid intersection. The ASAME experimental arrangement is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. ASAME strain measurement system

To establish the applicability of the above process to reinforcement deformation, experiments were carried out using Tech Textiles E-BXhd 936 $\pm 45^\circ$ reinforcement. This material is of particular interest, as it is designed to be a "high drape" reinforcement, in which inter-fibre slip is thought to be an important deformation mechanism. A 6.4 mm square grid was screen printed onto one surface of the fabric. The material was deformed over a number of male forms using a vacuum bag, with the deformed specimens maintained using a polyurethane aerosol varnish. The deformed grids were then scanned using the ASAME process to provide the position of each grid intersection. These were post-processed to calculate the local inter-fibre angle and grid spacings, which were used to estimate the local degree of inter-fibre slip (calculated as a percentage strain between intersections).

Five 120 mm diameter discs with heights of 7mm, 14mm, 19mm, 26mm and 38mm were used to establish the effect of depth of draw on fabric deformation. In each case, the fabric was considered in four quadrants, each of which were analyzed using the process detailed above. Drap analyses were carried out for each disc to enable comparison of the predicted and measured fibre architectures. The results suggested that the accuracy of the pin-jointed deformation model decreases with increasing disc height. This is demonstrated by Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, which show the predicted and measured fibre patterns for 7mm and 26mm discs respectively. In each case the surface is shaded to represent local shear, and for the measured patterns fibre segments are also shaded to indicate percentage inter-fibre slip. As the disc height was increased, inter-fibre slip became increasingly important resulting in a reduction in fabric shear. The minimum fibre angles observed in each quadrant and at each disc height are plotted in Fig. 8. This shows that although the predicted inter-fibre angle continued to reduce with increasing height, the measured angles levelled off at around 32° due to fibre locking. Any further deformation was accommodated by either inter-fibre slip or wrinkling.

The experiments described above suggest that although shear is probably the most important deformation mechanisms, some engineered fabrics may exhibit a considerable degree of inter-fibre slip for deep draw components. More generally the results suggest that the pin-jointed deformation model is applicable to relatively simple surface geometries where the fabric does not approach its practical locking angle. Both locking angle and the shear/slip relationship are thought to be fabric specific phenomena, which may be characterised using material deformation data. It is hoped that the ASAME process can be used to characterise a range of materials, both to establish the applicability of the current deformation model and to assist in the development of a more accurate simulation.

(a) Predicted pattern

(b) Measured pattern

Figure 6. Theoretical and experimental fibre distributions for 7mm disc

(a) Predicted pattern

(b) Measured pattern

Figure 7. Theoretical and experimental fibre distributions for 26mm disc

Figure 8. Minimum fibre angles for discs of varying height

SUMMARY

A technique has been developed which can establish the fibre distribution within a deformed engineered fabric. This may be used to validate the kinematic drape model developed by the authors, and can also provide formability data for specific reinforcements. In particular, the ability to establish the so called "locking angle", which indicates the onset of reinforcement wrinkling, has been demonstrated. The results of the experimental study would suggest that whereas drape modelling is usually based on the assumption that the fabric deforms by shear only, in reality relative fibre slip becomes increasingly important as the locking angle is approached. This would suggest that there may be a measurable shear/slip relationship which could be used to improve the accuracy of the model. It is hoped that the experimental method described in this paper may be used to establish this relationship.

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REFERENCES

1. M.J. Owen, V. Middleton and C.D. Rudd, Fibre reinforcement for high volume resin transfer moulding (RTM). *Composites Manufacturing* **1**, 74-78 (1990).

2. C.D. Rudd, and A.C. Long, Design strategies for fibre preforms, *Proc. 10th Annual ASM/ESD Advanced Composites Conf. (ACCE 94), Dearborn, USA, 277-287, (1994).*
3. R.E. Robertson, E.S. Hsiue, E.N. Sickafus and G.S.Y. Yeh, Fiber rearrangements during the moulding of continuous fibre composites. 1. Flat cloth to a hemisphere. *Polymer Composites 2, 126-131 (1981).*
4. B.P. Van West, R.B. Pipes and M. Keefe, A simulation of the draping of bidirectional fabrics over arbitrary surfaces. *J. Text. Inst. 448-460 (1990).*
5. O.K. Bergsa, Computer simulation of 3D forming processes of fabric reinforced plastics. *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. on Composite Materials (ICCM/9), Madrid, 560-567 (1993).*
6. D. Laroche, and T. Vu-Khanh, Forming of woven fabric composites. *J. Composite Materials 28, 1825-1839 (1994).*
7. A.C. Long, and C.D. Rudd, A simulation of reinforcement deformation during the production of preforms for liquid moulding processes. *IMechE J. of Eng. Manuf. 208, 269-278 (1994).*
8. A.K. Ghosh and S.S. Hecker, Failure in thin sheets stretched over rigid punches. *Metal. Trans. 6A, 1065-1074 (1975).*